

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Methodological guidelines to collect data and assess the costs of CF practices and associated MRV

MARVIC

Deliverable 5.1

Document Information

Grant agreement		101112942
Project title	Developing and testing a framework for the design of harmonized, context-specific Monitoring, Reporting and Verification systems for soil Carbon and greenhouse gas balances by agricultural activities	
Project acronym	MARVIC	
Project duration	48 months	
Coordinator	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Belgium	
Related work package(s)	WP5	
Related task(s)	T5.1	
Lead organisation	French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE)	
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Due date	M18	
Submission date		
Dissemination level	Public	

Document Revision History

Date	Version	Submitted by	Reviewed by
6/12/2024	1.0	Laure BAMIÈRE (INRAE)	Greet RUYSSCHAERT (ILVO), Berit HASLER (UCPH)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14230219

How to cite this report:

Bamière L., Louhichi K., Photinodellis R., Maitah M., Hasler B., Elofsson K. (2024). *Methodological guidelines to collect data and assess the costs of CF practices and associated MRV* (Deliverable 5.1 of MARVIC project, v1.0; p. 38).

Disclaimer

This research is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement: 101112942). The content of this deliverable reflects only the authors' views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. **Please note that this report has not yet been approved by the European Commission and is still under review.**

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Executive Summary

This report, a deliverable of the MARVIC project, provides methodological guidelines for collecting data and assessing the costs of carbon farming (CF) practices and the associated Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) methodologies. The data collected using these guidelines will serve as critical inputs for economic analyses conducted in workpackage 5 (WP5), supporting tasks such as i) assessing the economic impacts and cost-effectiveness of CF practices and schemes, accounting for MRV costs, ii) informing workshops on MRV systems in Test Cases (TCs), and iii) the evaluation of cost-effective regulatory schemes. They will also provide insight into the trade-offs between the cost and accuracy of the MRV methodologies that will be developed in MARVIC (WP2).

This document is intended for scientists and experts in charge of the 26 MARVIC Test Cases across Europe, covering a wide range of Land-Uses and Soil Types (LUSTs), i.e., arable land on mineral soils, grassland on mineral soils, managed peatland, and agroforestry/woody crops. It provides practical guidance for standardized data collection, ensuring consistency and comparability of results. It addresses the definition and assessment of various cost (and revenue) categories induced by the adoption of a carbon farming practice and the implementation of an MRV methodology: operational costs (e.g., fertilizers, seeds, labor), opportunity costs (e.g., foregone revenues), and transaction costs (e.g., time spent to gather information on carbon farming schemes and MRV expenses). MRV costs, as a subset of transaction costs, depend on the type of policy, the precision required by the latter, and the methodology used. The report provides practical examples of CF practice costs calculation (e.g., cover /catch crops agroforestry, and peatland rewetting) and an example of MRV cost (for the French Label Bas Carbon certification framework). These are illustrative examples only, and serve to demonstrate data collection and calculation methodologies.

Several options for MRV methodologies will be designed in the frame of the MARVIC project, for the different land use and soil types. Once they are available, WP1 will provide a list and a detailed description of the major MARVIC MRV methodologies, including a breakdown into main steps and potential cost items. This information will be used to draft a simple “MRV cost” spreadsheet to help Test Cases collect data and assess the costs of the relevant MRV methodologies for their specific context. WP2, WP3, and Test Cases will also provide information on the accuracy and uncertainty associated with the measurements, models, and operational processing chain tools used

to assess carbon removals. This information will be used in Task 5.1 economic models to assess the present and future economic impacts and cost-effectiveness of CF policies, accounting for MRV costs.

Table of Contents

Document Information.....	i
Document Revision History.....	i
Contributing partners	iii
Executive Summary.....	iv
Table of Contents	vi
Abbreviations and Acronyms	viii
1. Introduction.....	1
2. Carbon farming practices addressed in MARVIC	2
3. Cost categories.....	3
3.1 Operational costs.....	3
3.2 Benefits and revenues	4
3.3 Opportunity costs.....	4
3.4 Transaction costs	5
3.5 Monitoring, reporting, and verification costs.....	6
4. Basic principles for data collection	8
4.1 Standard unit for expressing costs and revenues	8
4.2 Time period	8
4.3 Representativeness.....	9
4.4 Transparency and documentation.....	9
5. Guidelines to assess costs.....	9
5.1 Cost of carbon farming practices	9
5.1.1 Example of the cost of cover crops in France	11
5.1.2 Example of the cost of intraplot agroforestry in France.....	12
5.1.3 Example of Catch crops (cover crops) in Denmark.....	14
5.1.4 Example of rewetting of peatland in Denmark	17
5.2 MRV costs of carbon farming practices	19
5.3 Summary of usual cost items and potential data sources	23
5.4 Review of existing information on CF practices costs and MRV costs	24
6. References	26
7. Appendices.....	29
Appendix I Data collection methods.....	29
Appendix II Cost and revenues for Cropland	31
Appendix III Agroforestry implementation cost.....	34
Appendix IV MRV cost breakdown in the example of the French Label Bas Carbone for Arable land	35

List of Tables

Table 1. Breakdown of the average additional cost for farmers, in euros per hectare and per year, to implement in the carbon farming practice consisting in introducing or extending the duration of cover crops in crop rotations, compared with the “current practice” scenario for mainland France. 12

Table 2. Breakdown of Agroforestry implementation cost (average constant annuity at the national level) per cost item. Nb: a positive/negative constant annuity represents a loss/gain for the Farmer, respectively. 14

Table 3. Costs of catch crops in Danish agriculture, EUR/ha..... 16

Table 4. Construction costs for establishing a rewetted peatland with closure of drains, €/ha 18

Table 5. Restoration costs of wetlands in Denmark..... 19

Table 6. Average costs and revenues of carbon farming (CF) practices, compared to baseline (i.e., current practices): cropland..... 31

Table 7 Schedule of cash flows associated with the implementation of the Agroforestry practice, net present value (NPV) and constant annuity (CA)..... 34

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AGg	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CD&E	Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CF	Carbon Farming
CFP	Carbon Farming Practice(s)
CFS	Carbon Farming Scheme(s)
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
LUST	Land Use x Soil Type
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification
TC	Test Case

1. Introduction

Reliable and accurate cost data on carbon farming (CF) practices and their monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems is crucial for assessing their cost-effectiveness and making informed, evidence-based decisions. By comparing the costs and benefits of different CF practices and schemes, decision-makers can: (i) assess whether carbon farming schemes can make a cost-effective contribution to climate targets; (ii) identify which practices and MRV schemes deliver the most significant carbon storage per euro spent; (iii) evaluate the economic feasibility of expanding these schemes to larger areas; (iv) estimate the government's and farmers' costs of implementing robust MRV systems, ensuring reliability and cost-effectiveness of CF schemes; and (v) identify the most suitable policy instruments and economic incentives to encourage widespread adoption of carbon farming practices.

However, collecting these data presents challenges. First, the wide range of carbon farming practices (e.g., agroforestry, cover /catch crops, no-till farming) and the heterogeneity of European farming systems make it difficult to establish a simple, standardized approach for data collection. Second, the cost of implementing CF practices varies based on local factors such as soil type, climate, water availability, and existing infrastructure. Third, the economic cost of family labor and the use of resources produced on the farm (e.g., grass used as fodder) can be difficult to quantify. Also, farmers may encounter administrative and transaction costs in carbon markets or carbon credit systems and other types of regulations to reduce carbon /GHG emissions (e.g., paperwork, certification costs, time spent on interaction with regulatory agencies, and costs related to monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems). These costs can vary substantially and data can be hard to find.

To obtain meaningful and policy-relevant information, the above-mentioned costs must be compared to the carbon sequestration effect achieved by the same measures. It is therefore necessary that these carbon impacts are calculated in a consistent manner, relevant from both a scientific and policy perspective. This requires that any initial investments necessary for CF practices (e.g., tree planting in the case of agroforestry) are appropriately distributed over the duration of the practice (i.e. until a new replacement investment becomes necessary).

The main goal of the Soil Mission MARVIC project is to develop a framework for the design of harmonized context-specific Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems for carbon farming, in support of the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming

regulation. This MRV framework will be applied in 26 test cases (TCs) across Europe, with a test case being a region or country for which an MRV methodology will be designed for a specific LUST (Land Use x Soil Type, i.e., arable on mineral soils, grassland on mineral soils, managed peatland, and agroforestry/woody crops).

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide guidance to MARVIC Test Cases and LUST leaders on data collection and the assessment of both carbon farming practices and associated MRV costs, relevant for their land use type and country. We first provide general definitions of the various types of costs (and revenues) induced by the adoption of a new practice and the implementation of an MRV methodology. Then we provide basic principles on how to assess them and five examples from existing studies or CF scheme. The information on CF practices and MRV costs that will be collected in the various MARVIC Test Cases will later be used in MARVIC Task 5.1 economic models, but also in Task 5.3 which will conduct workshops on MRV systems in TCs, and in Task 5.4 for the assessment of cost-effective regulatory schemes.

2. Carbon farming practices addressed in MARVIC

There are several carbon farming practices that can enhance carbon storage in agricultural systems and/or reduce greenhouse gas emissions including, e.g., cover cropping, no-till farming, biochar application, improved manure management, and agroforestry (Guerrero et al., 2024). The efficiency of these measures varies depending on local conditions such as soil type, climate, and existing agricultural practices. We will here focus on the following list provided by in MARVIC Deliverable 4.1 (Torrús-Castillo et al, 2024).

Arable land:

- Cropland: the carbon farming practices assessed in WP4 are catch/cover crops, crop rotations, reduced tillage, zero tillage, organic amendments and residue management.

Grassland:

- Permanent grassland: the carbon farming practices assessed in WP4 include maintenance of permanent grassland, reducing grassland renewal, optimising manure application, optimizing grazing intensity, and conversion of cropland to grassland.

Peatland:

- (Partial) Rewetting of peatlands e.g., raising the water table by only 10 or 20 cm, is considered as a comprehensive CF practice.

Agroforestry and woody crops:

- Sylvoarable agroforestry systems
- For woody crops, WP4 decided to limit the studied practices to: cover crops, manure or organic fertilizers, no tillage and tillage (used as a reference), and the combination of different management practices on the inter-rows.

We aim to evaluate each practice based on its potential for increased carbon storage and costs for farmers (including both costs for the practice itself and for MRV).

3. Cost categories

Estimating the costs of carbon farming (CF) practices requires accounting for all economic costs and revenues associated with their implementation. Economic costs differ from accounting costs as they encompass not only out-of-pocket (cash) expenses but also so-called opportunity costs. Other types of costs, such as monitoring, reporting, and verification costs, are associated with the implementation of CF schemes. Below, we provide a comprehensive definition of different types of costs and revenues for which data need to be collected.

3.1 Operational costs

Operational costs are costs accruing over the lifetime¹ of a CF practice. They include both direct and indirect costs. Direct costs include all immediate and tangible expenses related to the implementation of carbon farming practices, such as seeds, fertilizers, water, machinery, and hired labor. Indirect costs refer to costs that are not directly tied to carbon farming practices implementation but are necessary to support it, such as administrative costs. Indirect costs also include reduced input (e.g., water) or/and yield reduction for the following crop. Operational costs are often expressed in euros per hectare.

¹ The lifetime of a carbon farming practice is generally different and longer from the carbon farming scheme contract duration. For instance, in the case of agroforestry the period to be considered is at least until timber harvest or tree replanting, i.e. 50 years or more depending on the species. This is addressed in section 4.

3.2 Benefits and revenues

The revenue from carbon farming includes (i) revenues from the sale of additional products alongside traditional crops (i.e. equal to the unit price received from the sale of the product multiplied by the quantity sold), (ii) public financial incentives or subsidies offered to farmers who adopt carbon farming practices, such as grants or payments through environmental programs, and that can arise at the local, national or EU level, (iii) income from selling carbon credits in carbon markets, and (iv) other miscellaneous revenues, such as cost savings or increased yields generated by certain carbon farming practices.

Of particular interest is the farmer's net *additional* cost of CF practice compared to the current (or reference or baseline) practice. It corresponds to the additional operational costs minus the additional revenues and savings. A positive net additional cost represents a loss of profit for the farmer, while a negative net additional cost represents a gain. In the latter case, if the practice is not already implemented by the farmer, it is usually because other costs exist such as opportunity costs and transaction costs described below. And, indeed, if revenues from public policies or carbon credits are accounted for by the farmer, then they have to be balanced at least with MRV costs associated with the policy or credit certification.

3.3 Opportunity costs

The cost of a practice may be more difficult to measure if it is associated with a reallocation of resources within a farm, such as a change in crop mix and/or animal numbers. In such cases, economists prefer to use the term opportunity cost to evaluate a farming practice. The opportunity cost of a practice corresponds basically to the loss of income caused by forgoing more profitable production. For example, restoration of cultivated organic soils (drained peatlands) will require farmers to lose income from agricultural production. Similarly, farmers who retain crop residues could forgo income or cost savings from selling those residues or using them as livestock feed or bedding on the farm. So, in addition to the variation in direct expenses linked to the implementation of a new practice (operational costs), the opportunity cost takes into account all the variations in income generated by this change in practice or cropping activity. Farmers' production decisions are generally defined according to this notion: a farmer will adopt the alternative practice for which the opportunity cost is lowest. The opportunity cost of a carbon farming practice varies from one farm to another, and even

from one plot to another. For example, the opportunity cost of converting annual crops to silvo-arable agroforestry (or grassland) will be higher if the land is fertile, or if the initial crop is highly profitable (e.g. contract crops).

Opportunity costs of adopting new practices, such as CF practices, are ideally assessed using micro-economic farm models. These models determine the optimal allocation of resources at the farm level so as to maximize the farmer's gross margin. However, when such model is not available, it is still possible to account for part of the opportunity costs. For instance, if fodder yield decreases following the implementation of a CF practice, it can be valued at the purchase price of this fodder, if it exists, or at the price of a substitute feed ration. And in the case of agroforestry, the decrease in available arable land where trees are grown can be valued with the gross margin of the cash crop mix grown on the farm. This way, it accounts for both the loss of revenue and the avoided operational costs.

3.4 Transaction costs

Transaction costs, in the frame of carbon farming, represent the costs associated with the process of implementing and managing programs aimed at increasing carbon removals and reducing greenhouse gas emissions from the agricultural sector. These costs are not directly related to the agricultural activity itself, but to all accompanying activities. Transaction costs are not the same as MRV costs (detailed in the next section). However, MRV is the largest part of transaction costs. In addition to MRV costs, transaction costs include, for example, administrative costs (administration, contracts), education costs (training, consulting), costs of negotiating and organizing CF (finding partners in carbon markets, coordination between farmers and government organizations), and costs of certification and legal services.

Private transaction costs are associated with the implementation of new practices. These transaction costs are the expenses incurred by farmers for activities that do not directly increase carbon storage or reduce emissions. They can be measured in terms of working time and money, corresponding to the establishment or modification of their relations with their suppliers and/or customers for goods and services (including public authorities), which are necessary for technical and organizational change on the farm. These costs are referred to as private costs, to distinguish them from public transaction costs incurred by public or semi-public bodies.

A large proportion of transaction costs are made up of information gathering and negotiation costs, aimed at reducing the uncertainties and risks associated with change. From the farmer's point of view, the first step is to explore technical options and assess their suitability for his/her operation. Secondly, it involves acquiring information on the commercial and legal implications of possible changes, so as to approach the negotiation phase with his/her economic partners. Thirdly, it involves conducting the necessary negotiations with his/her partners and ensuring the execution of the contracts associated with the change, which include measures, controls, and payments.

The weight of private transaction costs in the total cost of a change in practice is a determining factor in the farmer's choice of whether or not to adopt it. Private transaction costs can decrease over time through the learning effect. And a way of improving cost-effectiveness is to achieve economies of scale in emissions reduction and/or carbon removals.

Transaction costs are actually highly dependent on the nature of the policy incentives and supporting measures put in place to encourage a given change in practice. From the point of view of economic efficiency, the reduction of private transaction costs is not an objective in itself, but these costs must be taken into account in the choice and design of policy instruments. This choice is generally subject to a trade-off between the required precision of the environmental results monitoring and the increased transaction costs associated with this precision.

Similarly, the implementation of policies to encourage farmers to adopt carbon farming practices can generate significant additional costs for the State, referred to as **public transaction costs**, such as information and verification costs, negotiation costs, etc.

3.5 Monitoring, reporting, and verification costs

MRV costs are a special type of costs within the transaction costs category. The MRV costs can be private or public, depending on who is paying for the monitoring, reporting, and verification. E.g., if a public body provides standardised baselines, it is a public transaction costs and this reduces private transaction costs. Furthermore, the development of MRV methodologies would be a public transaction cost, but it is out of scope for this study.

MRV costs in the context of carbon farming include a wide range of activities and services that ensure accurate measurement and verification of changes in carbon stocks and

GHG emissions. The two basic monitoring (M) methods of MRV are: (i) repeated field measurements, and (ii) field measurement in combination with modelling. In addition to this, there are costs for reporting (R) and verification (V). MRV costs will accrue to the intermediary or agency responsible for a CF scheme, including technical costs (for building up the operational systems, information systems for carbon tracking, and bridging various existing databases) and as transaction costs (time requirements in operating the systems, including ensuring their transparency and liability). These costs can accrue both before and during the implementation of a CF scheme. MRV costs also accrue to farmers, e.g., private transaction costs related to the time requirements for various monitoring and reporting activities allocated to the farmer himself/herself.

Monitoring (M) refers to measuring soil carbon levels using methods (i) or (ii) mentioned above. In both methods a pivotal task is the assessment of baseline (this is done by a public body (in case of standardised baselines) or the certifying company, and represents a transaction cost. The measuring method (i) induces technical costs for equipment as well as transaction costs related to time to collect and analyze soil samples to assess carbon stock levels and changes therein, and time and transport costs for traveling from the monitoring intermediary or agency to and from the farm. In case (ii), there are also costs related to modelling, building up the operational systems, and bridging different databases as well as costs for time spent operating the systems. An example of bridging databases is the transfer and re-use of anonymized data on management practices applied at the field/farm; or, transfer and re-use of soil monitoring data from national surveys. In sum, monitoring costs include *ex-ante* costs (accruing before the onset of the project) as well as operational costs during the project. These categories of costs accrue to the project operator. Additionally, there are monitoring costs that accrue to the farmer (such as technical costs for consultancy and transaction costs as a time requirement for the preparation of a monitoring plan at farm-level).

Reporting (R) refers to the systematic documentation and presentation of the monitored information. This can vary in format, from detailed technical reports to simple summaries for public disclosure. This aspect is often required by regulatory bodies and can also be used for transparency and stakeholder communication. Reporting costs thus include the cost of making farm management data available within the duration of the CFS project, and the cost of reporting (annually) to the certification body.

Verification (V) refers to external audits ensuring the project meets the standards (transaction costs via time requirements of the audit staff and farmer who receives

auditors). Further, verification can include operations with reserve funds that cover the risks of failed projects (e.g. insurance policy or similar guarantee mechanisms) as a transaction cost accruing to the certifying company.

Additionally, for MRV to function effectively, it is important to take into account private or public services that provide information, training, and advisory support to the farmer/user and the certifying company. These costs are out of scope in this study.

4. Basic principles for data collection

In the following, we provide some basic principles for data collection that are widely recognized across research and practical applications. Three data collection methods are described in detail in Appendix I.

4.1 Standard unit for expressing costs and revenues

It is important that data on revenues and costs are collected and reported for the same unit. This means that if data are collected for a specific land area, then both revenues and costs must be aligned with that same area. Costs and revenues are usually expressed in euros per hectare for crop activities, and fixed costs in euros per farm. To ensure consistency and comparability, costs need to be collected using a consistent method across different data sources, regions or time periods.

4.2 Time period

It is essential that the collected revenues and costs for a given CF practice correspond to the same time period, such as a typical growing season or a calendar year or a lifetime. Costs and revenues can also be adjusted to different time periods, provided that adjustments for inflation and the time value of money are accurately applied.

Additionally, given that some CF practices are based on annual actions (e.g. cover crops) while others on multiannual actions (e.g. agroforestry), the costs and benefit associated with the multiannual practice must be assessed along the practice's lifetime using the net present value (NPV) method and then divided by the annuity factor to obtain the equivalent annual annuity, which can be compared with the costs and benefits of annual actions. The calculation of NPV requires selecting an appropriate discount rate, which is often a challenging task. EU recommendation for climate change mitigation projects is 3% (EC, 2023).

4.3 Representativeness

The data should be representative of the country as a whole, taking into account farms heterogeneity (specialization and size) and geographical differences. Ideally, this should be based on an appropriate sampling method of regions, soil and farm types, etc., to minimize bias and ensure the findings are representative. When this is the case, results can be generalized across various contexts.

4.4 Transparency and documentation

Ensure that all data sources are well-documented, including where the data comes from, how it was collected, and any assumptions used. This allows others to understand, replicate, or validate the data. Clearly define each cost category (e.g., input costs, fixed costs at the farm level) and how they are calculated to avoid ambiguity. A template like **Error! Reference source not found.** in Appendix II will be later discussed with and provided to Test Cases for the collection and documentation of data.

5. Guidelines to assess costs

5.1 Cost of carbon farming practices

To assess the net additional cost of a change in practice, compared to the baseline or reference situation, it is generally necessary to account for:

- changes in inputs use: e.g., organic and mineral fertilizer, pesticides, herbicides, seeds, irrigation water, animal feeding, biochar.
- changes in cropping operations /machinery: including energy, labour, and depreciation or service provision by a third-party.
- changes in yields: e.g., crop, fodder, milk, meat.
- dedicated investments: e.g., planting tree lines or hedges and the life time of these investments.
- creation of new revenues: e.g., selling of wood / nuts / fruits in the case of agroforestry.
- foregone revenues: e.g., when some crop area is substituted with tree lines, hedges, grassland or wetland.

To assess the costs and potential gains associated with the implementation of an "annual" CF practice, the changes generated by the latter at farm level are listed and compared with the reference situation or practice. After quantifying these modifications in units per hectare (or farm) ($Q_{m,t}$), a unit price is associated with them (in €/unit) to calculate the cost of the CFP (CFP_C) in € per year and per hectare (or farm). Depending on whether the modification corresponds to an expense or an income, the price indicated is positive or negative, respectively (see Equation 1). Thus, if CFP_C is positive the CF practice generates a net loss for the farmer, while if CFP_C is negative, the CF practice generates a net profit for the farmer.

Equation 1: Basic formula to calculate the net additional cost of a CF practice

$$CFP_C_t = \sum_{m=1}^M Q_{m,t} * price_{m,t}$$

With:

- $t \in [0, T]$ the year and T the time horizon considered, i.e. the practice lifetime
- $m \in [0, M]$ the type of modifications induced by the change in practice, compared to the baseline
- $Q_{m,t}$ the quantity associated with the modification m induced by the change in practice in year t, in units per hectare (or farm)
- $price_{m,t}$ the unit Price associated with m, in €/unit

In the case of CF practices requiring an initial investment and with costs or income that are not regular or delayed over time, we calculate the constant annuity (loss or gain) which would be equivalent for the farmer over the practice lifetime. The first step is to calculate the net present value (NPV) associated with the CF practice and then the equivalent constant annuity (CA) (see Equation 2). This requires the use of a discount rate reflecting the preference for present revenues over future ones.

Equation 2: Formula to assess the net present value (NPV) and the equivalent constant annuity (CA) of a carbon farming practice

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{CFP_C_t}{(1+i)^t}$$

$$CA = NPV * \frac{i}{1 - (1+i)^T}$$

With:

- $t \in [0, T]$ the year and T the time horizon, i.e. the lifetime of the practice.
- i the discount rate

It is worth noting that ready to use NPV and CA functions are available in MS Excel spreadsheets. A tentative template table for data collection and a detailed description of cost calculation in the frame of MARVIC is available in Appendix II.

5.1.1 Example of the cost of cover crops in France

We consider here a carbon farming practice consisting in a spatial or temporal expansion of cover crops on arable land in mainland France (Bamière et al, 2023; Pellerin & Bamière et al, 2020).

In areas where cover crops are already sown, their temporal extension ranges from 0.5 to 4 months and induces no additional cost. However, the longer growing period allows for more biomass production and, hence, higher carbon input to soil.

Where no cover crops are sown, the baseline or reference practice consists in leaving the soil bare after harvesting and using a stubble cultivator i) after harvesting to bury residues and ii) before sowing the following crop. With the insertion of new cover crops, in all fallows lasting more than two months, the farmer will have to buy seeds, sow the cover crop, irrigate it at sowing where necessary if s.he is equipped, and plough (using a moldboard) to destroy the cover crop before implanting the following crop. CC implantation can also have an upward or downward impact on the yield of the following crop.

The cost of seeds depends on the type of cover crop sown: €15/ha for mustard, €35/ha for ryegrass, €72.5/ha for vetch, €70/ha for faba beans in the French case. Seeding is generally carried out at the same time as stubble ploughing, which is simplified tillage. The seed drill is then attached to the stubble cultivator, except for faba beans and vetch, which require a specific cropping operation as their seeds are larger. A first pass of the stubble cultivator combined to the seed drill is priced at the cost of the stubble cultivator (28 €/ha). For vetch and faba beans, the second pass is priced at the cost of the seed drill (36.70 €/ha). Irrigation is capped at 3 mm, i.e. 30 m³, with a water price of 0.29 €/m³. Ploughing to destroy the cover crop is estimated at €124/ha, replacing superficial tillage estimated at €102/ha. The STICS model simulated yield variations for the cash crops, then expressed in percentage points. The variation in revenue was estimated by applying this percentage to the yield calculated in the French Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) (in t/ha), valued by the crop price (in €/t) also taken from the FADN.

This information is used to calculate the cost of changing practices at the scale of crop rotations, before aggregating the costs at the region and national level. Compared with the baseline or reference scenario, introducing or extending the duration of cover crops in crop rotations results in additional costs for the farmer, of about €39/ha on average for the whole of mainland France. This is the result of an increase in costs of €69/ha, partly offset by an increase in revenue of €30/ha. The principal expenses correspond to the purchase of seeds (€29/ha), as well as the use of machinery for sowing and destroying the CC (€29/ha) (see Table 1).

Table 1. Breakdown of the average additional cost for farmers, in euros per hectare and per year, to implement in the carbon farming practice consisting in introducing or extending the duration of cover crops in crop rotations, compared with the “current practice” scenario for mainland France. (translated from Pellerin & Bamière et al (2020))

Cost items	in €/ha of area base/year
Seeds	28.83
Stubble cultivator	11.74
Seed drill	14.24
Irrigation	10,46
Destruction of CC	3.39
Yield variations	-30.03
Total cost	38.64

5.1.2 Example of the cost of intraplot agroforestry in France

The “agroforestry” practice studied by INRAE for the French agricultural sector (Pellerin & Bamière et al. (2020), Bamière et al. (2023)) involves the introduction of trees within a cultivated plot at an initial density of 75 trees per ha for a 12.5% footprint - including the grass strip. Trees were planted in rows spaced every 22.5 m (cultivated alley = 21 m, grass strip = 3 m). The species were chosen for their value as timber – 50% hybrid walnut (*Juglans regia x nigra*) and 50% wild cherry (*Prunus avium*). Planting requires several operations – advice, picketing, soil preparation, tree planting, protection and mulching at the tree's base, and sowing of a grass cover. From year 7 onwards, the vegetation in the grass strip at the foot of the trees is roto-tilled every year to prevent the dispersion of seeds into crops. Trees are replanted in the second year to replace those that have failed to take root. They then undergo a shaping pruning from year 1 to year 7 and are pruned every year from year 4 to year 15. In year 10, the tree line is thinned to 49 trees per hectare, which are harvested 50 years after planting. As the aim is to store carbon, the stumps are left in the field after harvesting. In the cultivated alleys, cropping practices

remain unchanged. Crop production remains unaffected for the first 15 years, but from year 16 onwards, a 10% reduction is applied to crop yields until the trees are cut down in year 50. Implementation of this practice is limited to plots larger than one hectare, with a soil depth greater than one metre, and non-hydromorphic soil.

The cost of implementing the agroforestry practice takes into account: the costs and benefits associated with planting, maintaining, and harvesting the tree lines, the opportunity costs associated with the 12.5% loss of cultivated area to the benefit of the tree lines, and the opportunity costs associated with reduced crop yields in the inter-row. They are discounted at a rate of 4.5%, recommended by the French government at the time (Quinet et al., 2013), and lead to the calculation of a constant annuity.

Tree row planting and maintenance costs:

- Advice, picketing, and soil preparation:
 - Advice: 24 h/project of 10 ha at 62.5€/h, i.e., 150 €/ha.
 - Picketing: negligible cost regarding supplies, 2 hours work at €19/hour, i.e., €38/ha.
 - Soil preparation: decompacting and ploughing for a total cost of €177/ha.
- Tree planting and protection:
 - Tree planting: 75 trees at €1.66/plant and 2.5 h/ha of work, i.e. €172/ha.
 - Protection and mulching: €5/tree and 4h of work, i.e. €451/ha.
 - Sowing of grass cover: 19 €/ha.
- Maintenance:
 - Annual maintenance of the grass strip with a rotofil (from year 7 onwards): 1.5 h/ha, i.e., 29 €/ha
 - Regarnishing (year 2): 15% of trees to be replaced and 2 h/ha, i.e. 57€/ha.
 - Shaping pruning of young trees (years 1 to 7): 5 mn/stem or 119 €/ha.
 - Pruning (years 4 to 15): 3 mn/tree (travel, pruning, and removal of branches) from year 4 to 10, 5min/tree from year 10 to 12, 8 mn/tree from year 13 to 15, 25% of trees in year 4, 50% of trees in year 5, 100% of trees from year 6 to year 12, 50% of trees from year 13 to 15, i.e., 18 to 77€/ha depending on the year.
 - Thinning (year 10): 35% of trees removed, 12 mn/tree and chipping at 0.39 €/tree, i.e., 110€/ha.

Income from wood production

- Sale of pruning wood: 0.013 stere/tree at 35 €/stere, i.e., from 9€ to 34 €/ha/year depending on the year.
- Sale of thinning wood (year 10): 0.17 m³/tree at 56 €/m³, i.e., 250 €/ha.
- Final sale of timber (year 50): 2.47 m³/tree valued at 200 €/m³, i.e., 2,680 €/ha.

Opportunity costs: loss of cultivated area and lower yields

- The opportunity costs associated with the loss of cultivated area (12.5%) to tree lines correspond to the loss of gross margin of the associated crops. These gross margins are estimated from FADN data. The average cost at the national level is 72 €/ha/year.
- The 10% decrease in crop yields, starting in year 16, results in a reduction in revenue proportional to the selling price of the crops. Yields and prices for each crop are taken from the FADN. The average cost at the national level is 46.5 €/ha.

Based on this information, a cash flow schedule is drawn up (see Appendix III Agroforestry implementation cost) and used to calculate the net present value of all the costs and benefits associated with the “Agroforestry” practice, and then the associated constant annuity. The breakdown of the constant annuity by cost item is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Breakdown of Agroforestry implementation cost (average constant annuity at the national level) per cost item. Nb: a positive/negative constant annuity represents a loss/gain for the Farmer, respectively. Source (Bamière et al. (2022a, <https://doi.org/10.57745/10XJV0>), Bamière et al. (2023))

	Average constant annuity (€/ha-1)
Setting up the agroforestry system (advice, picketing, soil preparation, planting, etc.)	85
Maintenance of tree lines	49
Sale of wood (pruning and thinning)	-16
Sale of wood (final harvest)	-153
Loss of cultivated area (foregone gross margins)	72
Yield reduction on remaining cultivated area	47
Total cost to farmer	84

5.1.3 Example of Catch crops (cover crops) in Denmark

Growing catch crops (or cover crops) is a measure to reduce nitrogen leaching from Danish cropland, but is also considered a measure to reduce CO₂e and thus a carbon

farming measure. The following cost estimations are from Eriksen et al. (2020), which is a catalogue of nitrogen abatement measures in Danish agriculture. The costs are measured in 2018 prices. The costs presented here are costs for the farmer, but without any subsidies provided.

The following types of catch crop can be used: cruciferous crops, pure grass without clover, bluebells, oil raddish, chicory and seed grass, which after harvest continues as a catch crop.

The costs of catch crops include:

1. Costs for establishing the crop, including seeds.
2. Savings on the purchase of nitrogen as a result of the nutrient effect from the catch crop
3. The opportunity costs of any crop rotation change required to establish catch crops.

In addition to these effects the catch crops can, to a lesser extent, lead to an increase in operational costs (increased harvesting, increased weeds and need for management) and also yield loss if the nutrient effect is overestimated. This nutrient effect has to be included in the estimation of the nitrogen input to the field in the fertiliser accounts required from each farm, and the fertilization level (manure and inorganic fertilizer) has to be reduced accordingly.

Establishment costs

The costs for establishing catch crops can vary from no costs, if the catch crops are established by seeds from the previous crop, up to 800 DKK/ha (108 €/ha), if expensive types of catch crops are used and where row-sowing is applied.

If the catch crop is established by seeds of yellow mustard or oil radish, the costs are estimated to be constituted mainly of the seeds costs, which are in the range of 130-230 DKK/ha (i.e., 18 - 31 €/ha) (SEGES, 2018).

The catch crops are typically sown by centrifugal spreaders, or by row-sowing techniques, which are more expensive than the spreaders. Row sowing is used when seeds with varying seed weight are used, as this type of seeds will tend to unmix by centrifugal dispersal. In Eriksen et al. (2020), cost figures from FarmtalOnline from

SEGES² are used, and the average cost of centrifugal spreading is 143 DKK/ha (19€/ha), while the average cost of row sowing is 380 DKK/ha (51€/ha). In Eriksen et al (2020), it is assumed that the sowing costs are in the 125 – 400 DKK /ha range (17-54€/ha).

Savings on the purchase of nitrogen fertilizer as a result of the nutrient effect from the catch crop

The nutrient effect from the catch crop is 17 kg N/ha when catch crops are grown on fields without animal manure application. The nutrient effect is 25 kg N/ha for fertilized fields where animal manure is applied.

Assuming a fertiliser price of 7.61 DKK/kg N (1 €/kg) the nutrient value corresponds to 129 DKK/ha (17€/ha) and 190 DKK/ha (26 €/ha), respectively. The costs ítems and the total costs are calculated and shown in €/ha in Table 3.

Table 3. Costs of catch crops in Danish agriculture, EUR/ha

Catch crop	Sowing method	Seeds	Operational costs	Nutrient effect	Total costs to farmer
		€/ha	€/ha (machinery)	€/ha*	€/ha
Seeds from former crop (grass)	-	0	17-26**	-17 to -26	0
Cheap mix	Centrifugal spread	27	17	16-26	18-26
Expensive mix	Centrifugal spread	54	17	16-26	45-54

*the nutrient effect of catch crops is a negative cost, i.e. a saved fertiliser cost

** the operational costs of treating the withered catch crop are anticipated to be equal to saved costs from reduced fertilizers (the nutrient effect) (Eriksen et al, page 49).

Opportunity cost There are two types of catch crops establishments – either they are established in or after a spring cereal, or they are established at a former winter cereal field, where the cultivation is changed from winter cereals to spring cereals to allow for the catch crop. When the rotational change from winter to spring crops is required, there will be an opportunity cost, which is the difference in the revenue (the gross margin) from

² SEGES (SEGES Innovation) is an independent research and innovation company. Farmtal online is delivered annually by SEGES.

<https://farmtalonline.dlbr.dk/Navigation/NavigationTree.aspx>

winter crops to the revenue (gross margin) of spring crops. On average, this opportunity cost is 1,361 DKK/ha (184 €/ha) for sandy soils, where the gross margin is relatively low because of a low yield, and 2,499 DKK/ha per hectare (338 €/ha) on clay soils, where the yields and gross margins are higher.

The gross margin is the revenue retained after the direct costs have been subtracted, i.e., the labor costs, seeds, fertilizer, and machinery. In the figures above labor costs are included with the sowing method.

5.1.4 Example of rewetting of peatland in Denmark

Rewetting of peatlands is a measure with high attention for climate mitigation because of the carbon sequestration potential of these fields. Still, there is limited experience with the implementation of the measure.

There are at least three ways that the rewetting can occur, either by interrupting or changing drains creating a temporary wet area, or by (re)constructing a wetland.

All three measures are required to be localized at organic soils with a 6% organic content or higher. A common cost to all three measures is the measurement and mapping to localize the organic content of soils, which Aarhus University typically does. This cost is not included in the establishment cost referenced here and is not measured to our knowledge. The costs of the three types of rewetting are estimated and described in Eriksen et al. (2020), a catalogue of measures to advise the implementation of the Water Framework Directive in Denmark. The costs of the measures are the same when used for carbon sequestration, A similar and updated list of measures will be assessed for the costs of climate mitigation from agriculture during 2025 for the new Ministry of the Trepartite.

The costs for the farmers of the **interruption of drains** include the opportunity costs of the production forgone, i.e., the loss of income associated with the changed land use. This cost is measured as averaged for clay and sandy soils for typical crop rotations. It is also possible to model them for the actual crops in the field for a 5-year period using a Danish environmental-economic land use model TargetEcon (Filippelli et al., 2024). Implementing the measure is associated with construction costs for disconnecting drains and digging distribution channels. Both tasks are thought to be carried out using a 30-ton excavator. Data on already rewetted peatlands have been retrieved from the Nature Agency, and from that, it is assumed that it takes 8 machine hours to close drains in

connection with the establishment of 1 ha of peatland. In the present context, in addition to closing drains, digging is also required for the distributor channels, so the number of machine hours per ha is estimated to be slightly higher and is set to 12 hours per ha. The hourly price for a 30-ton excavator is the one used by the Nature Agency (950 DKK/hour - 128 €/ha); in addition, a start-up cost of DKK 4,000 per project (541 € per project) to cover the transport of machinery to and from the project area is accounted for. Based on these prices, the costs for construction work in connection with the establishment of irrigated areas can be calculated at 15,400 DKK for the first hectare (2081 €/ha), plus 11,400 DKK/ha for the subsequent ones (1541 €/ha). In Table 4, the costs for construction work are calculated for two different area sizes, respectively 1 ha and 5 ha. The costs have been converted to annual costs for a time horizon of 20 years, based on a discount rate of 4%.

Table 4. Construction costs for establishing a rewetted peatland with closure of drains, €/ha

Size of the rewetted peatland	1 hectare	5 hectares
Construction costs (€)	541	541
Closure of drains (€)	1541	7703
Construction total	2081	8243
Construction €/ha total	2081	1649
Annual costs (€/ha, 4% discount rate*, 20 years depreciation)	153	121

*4% is used as this was the Danish governmental recommendation at the time (2020).

Another rewetting alternative for peatlands is **controlled drainage**, by controlling drainage systems to secure higher groundwater levels, regulated via an overflow in wells connected to the main drain. Hereby, hydrological conditions are changed when more water is stored in the root zone, and the drainage runoff is reduced. On most of the areas identified as suitable for this measure, it can be calculated that a control well must be established for every 1-2 ha. The construction costs per ha will vary between DKK 4,000 and 12,000, i.e., 540-1620 €/ha. The time required to manually regulate the water level twice a year is modest.

For both of these rewetting measures, there will be an opportunity cost corresponding to the loss of agricultural production. On average, this opportunity cost is 1,193 DKK/ha (161 €/ha) for sandy soils, where the gross margin is relatively low because of a low yield, and 3,027 DKK/ha (409 €/ha) on clay soils, where the yields and gross margins are higher.

The last type of rewetting measure on peatlands is constructed or re-established **wetlands**. Wetlands consist of several types, where the type affects the costs and the carbon removal effects. The main types of restored wetlands are formerly wet areas that receive water from streams, smaller drains, and ditches as well as areas that are flooded by stream water.

The costs associated with the implementation of wetlands as a means of action consist of construction costs, as well as the loss of income from the fields. The construction costs are estimated based on data from the Danish Agency for Agriculture. This database provides information on costs for measuring the feasibility of restoring wetlands (including hydrological conditions), the payments for realized restoration projects covering the establishment costs, and the restored wetland area during the period 2015-2019.

This information is presented in Table 5 and used for calculating the establishment costs, including the operational costs for the construction. The costs are annualized using a discount rate of 4% and a project lifetime of 20 years.

Table 5. Restoration costs of wetlands in Denmark

	€/ha/year
Time horizon	20 years
Preinvestigation	83
Construction costs	386
Total	468

For wetlands, there will also be opportunity costs for the agricultural production forgone on the affected fields. So, in addition to the costs of 468 €/ha for wetland establishment, there will be an additional average cost of 161 €/ha for sandy soils and 409 €/ha for clay soils, where the yields and gross margins are higher.

5.2 MRV costs of carbon farming practices

The evaluation of MRV costs depends on the processes and tools used, which can vary from one MRV method to another. The main items to consider in estimating these costs are as follows:

- **Labor costs for farmers:** to provide the farm management data and for reporting

- **Labor costs for technicians and other categories:** including field travel, data collection, on-site measurements and laboratory analyses (if there is soil analysis), and to parameterize and run simulation tools or models
- **Equipment and consumables costs:** Equipment for measurement, soil analysis kits, laboratory machinery, or unit price for sampling and analyses at commercial labs
- **Cost of using simulation tools or models:** including license fees
- **Cost of accessing to and processing remote sensing data:** if there is remote sensing monitoring
- Transaction costs, e.g. to establish a contract in the frame of a carbon farming scheme
- **Cost of audits:** for final certification

The choice of method and the amount of these costs are highly dependent on the precision required for estimating carbon removals. MRV costs could be zero or infinitely large for the same amount of carbon removals, depending on the chosen MRV protocols, and the only thing that could differ in that case is the accuracy of the measurement or the model's result. This is why it is important to provide quantitative information on the accuracy along with the cost of the MRV protocols assessed in Test Cases.

Several options for MRV methodologies will be designed in the frame of the MARVIC project, by WP1-2-3, for the different land use and soil types (LUSTs). WP1 will provide a list and a detailed description of the major MARVIC MRV methodologies, including a breakdown into main steps and potential cost items. When ready, this information will be used to draft a simple "MRV cost" spreadsheet to help Test Cases collect data and assess the costs of the relevant MRV methodologies for their specific context. Costs can occur at different scales (field, farm, etc.). The output will, therefore, include this information and also information on who does what and bears which cost among the various stakeholders. WP2, WP3, and Test Cases will also provide information on the accuracy and uncertainty associated with the measurements, models, and operational processing chain tools used to assess carbon removals. All this information will be used in Task 5.1 economic models to assess the present and future economic impacts and cost-effectiveness of CF policies, accounting for MRV costs.

MARVIC final MRV methodologies are not yet available, this is why we provide here an example of real-life MRV cost assessment in the frame of the French Label Bas Carbone for arable land.

Example of the French Label Bas Carbone for arable land

This section explains the main steps of the MRV process in arable land using two different tools –[Carbon Extract](#) (developed by Agrosolutions) and [CAP'2ER](#) (developed by [IDELE](#), the French technical institute for livestock breeding)– which comply with the [Label Bas Carbone](#) (a French certification framework) for the [arable land method](#).

Carbon Extract is used by agricultural cooperatives that pay Agrosolutions for its use. These cooperatives either provide this service, or part of it, for free to its member farmers or charge carbon farming project developers. In this example, we provide MRV costs for a situation where the cooperative covers most expenses, with the farmer contributing a small portion.

For Carbon Extract, the first step is an initial assessment of the farm, during which a trained technician from the agricultural cooperative visits the farm and collects data from the farmer. This includes:

- Weather data
- Soil data (such as clay content, lime, initial carbon, nitrogen, pH, etc.) is based on the most recent soil analysis (field measurements + laboratory analysis). The analysis is not specifically conducted for this initial assessment, but farmers generally have soil analysis done regularly, as they are required to do so annually if they have more than 3 ha in vulnerable zones (EU Nitrates Directive). This can also be required for certain CAP subsidies. It should be noted that the Label Bas Carbone does not impose a specific maximum date for the most recent analysis.
- Activity data from the past three years (crop rotations, yields, irrigation, field management practices, etc.).

This data collection allows for the grouping of plots into cropping systems (based on their management practices and soil type). When data are missing (or if no soil analysis has been done), generic data from public databases are used. The technician then enters these data into the Carbon Extract tool, which is linked to the [SIMEOS-AMG](#) carbon stock evolution simulation model. The tool also accounts for GHG emissions, using emission factors based on Tier 1 to Tier 3 methods. Next, the technician runs simulations to first obtain the initial carbon balance: the average annual change in soil carbon stock over the past three years, as well as the average annual GHG emissions over the same period. The technician presents the various carbon farming practices defined in the tool to the farmer. The farmer selects a combination of CF practices that (s)he can/is willing to implement. The technician then runs the new simulations. Several simulations can be

run (up to a maximum of five per farm) to test different scenarios of practice combinations, from which the farmer selects one. The simulation gives the estimated values for carbon removals and the change in GHG emissions, against the baseline, over the next five years. This allows for an estimation of the payment the farmer could receive at the end of the project (based on the current average carbon price). Depending on these results, the farmer decides whether to commit to the project and initiate the process or not. This first step costs €1,000-1,500 for the cooperative, including only the technician's labor (and not the cost of the tool's license and technician training), and €250 for the farm (see first table in Appendix IV for more details).

The second step is monitoring. Each year, the technician updates the activity data (but not the soil data) by collecting documents and information from the farmer without visiting the farm. This allows for the update of carbon sequestration estimates and GHG emissions over the 5-year period. While this annual monitoring step is not currently mandatory, it is helpful since this information will be needed for the audit at the end of the project and it is easier to collect it incrementally. In Version 2 of the Label Bas Carbone (currently being drafted), it is proposed that this annual monitoring will become mandatory. This step costs €250 per year for the cooperative, which includes only the technician's labor, and €50 per year for the farm (see second table in Appendix IV for more details).

The final step is the verification phase. At this stage, the technician submits all documents (including activity and soil data), as well as the simulation results on carbon sequestration and emissions reduction, to an independent auditor. This auditor is responsible for verifying that the results are compliant and writes an audit report. It should be noted that the tool, in this case, Carbon Extract, must also be compliant and has to be audited beforehand; and it is the responsibility of the tool's owner, Agrosolutions, to bear the cost of this audit. Currently, there is no estimate of costs for this step, as it has not yet been carried out; the first projects following the arable land method of the Label Bas Carbone will reach the five-year mark in 2025.

For CAP'2ER, IDELE³ covers the costs of the diagnosis and monitoring for the farmer, under the "Bon diagnostic Carbone" programme., The main steps of the MRV process

³ IDELE is a technical institute dedicated to improving the competitiveness of herbivore farming. It is funded by public funds, the Casdar fund, and through the revenue from a tax on french farmers' turnover.

are largely the same as for Carbon Extract. It is worth noting that IDELE has also developed a monitoring method for GHG emissions related to livestock, which, in addition to the previously mentioned steps, includes a mid-term visit (at three years) by the technician to verify that the practices are being properly implemented by the farmer (see details in third table in Appendix IV Appendix IV MRV cost breakdown in the example of the French Label Bas Carbone for Arable land).

5.3 Summary of usual cost items and potential data sources

The usual information necessary to assess practices costs are :

- Prices of inputs, such as cost of mineral N fertilizer (€/ kgN), irrigation water, seeds, fuel, etc.
- Prices of outputs such as cash and fodder crops, wood, etc.
- Cost of labour for various categories: e.g. 1h worktime farmer, 1h worktime technical advisor, 1h worktime auditor, etc.
- Information on current practices and cropping techniques.
- Yields per hectare for crops, fodder crops, grassland, etc.
- Cropping operation/machinery costs, such as cost of ploughing (€/ha), of reduced tillage, of spreading manure or mineral fertilizer, etc.
- Specific cost items related to tree planting and maintenance

The usual information necessary to assess MRV costs, in addition to the description of the MRV protocol, are:

- Cost of labor for various categories: e.g., 1h worktime farmer, 1h worktime technical advisor, 1h worktime auditor, etc.
- Fixed and variable costs for soil sampling: e.g., travel time to the field, cost to make one sample, store it, analyze it, including material and labor.
- Fixed and variable costs of using soil carbon / crop models: license, skilled operator worktime and cost, etc.
- Cost of data required to run model and/or assess soil carbon stock evolution, or time to collect them
- Cost of tools used by farmers or project agregators to report SOC stocks/storage

When the objective is to assess CF practices and MRV costs consistently at the national or EU level, then it is better to use public statistics and data as far as possible, such as FADN and Eurostat data. When such data are not available, then it is common to resort

to expert knowledge or local data. When it comes to assessing a CF project for a real farm or group of farmers, then real/onsite data can be used.

Note that, in MARVIC, WP2 is developing strategies for the smart use of diverse data sources, data acquisition techniques, and tools to support MRV activities, which could potentially reduce costs. For instance, the Metadata Catalogue (Task 2.1) harvests soil data, farm activity data, climatic data, land use types, vegetation types (e.g., agroforestry and woody crops), and other exogenous data from databases like FSDN (Farm sustainability data network), CORINE, ESDAC (European Soil DATA Centre), EUSO (EU Soil Observatory), and other repositories, specifying minimum temporal and spatial resolutions for MRV. And in Task 2.5, a survey is conducted to investigate the availability and interoperability, in all test cases, of farm activity data from IACS (Integrated Administration and Control Systems), FMIS (Farm Management Information Systems), and other sources. The use of interoperable data could save time and reduce MRV costs.

The discount rate to be used to assess climate change mitigation projects is usually provided by governments, in accordance with their commitments in terms of carbon budget. In the frame of MARVIC, we will use the same discount rate of 3% across all TCs, corresponding to the one recommended by the EU Commission (European Commission, “Better Regulation Toolbox,” Jul. 2023, <https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2023-09/BR%20toolbox%20-%20Jul%202023%20-%20FINAL.pdf>. [Accessed: Dec. 19, 2023])

5.4 Review of existing information on CF practices costs and MRV costs

A short review of existing data sources on CF practices costs and on potential transaction and MRV costs related to CF schemes has been carried out to provide T5.1 EU and French level economic models with provisional data until test case data are available.

Information on CF practices cost and mitigation potential, including carbon sequestration, can be found in Pérez Domínguez et al. (2020) and Frank et al. (2024) at the EU level, and in Bamière et al. (2023) for France. Sources on detailed MRV methodologies costs are less frequent. [Deloitte](#) carried out an inventory of existing MRV tools inventory for the 4per1000 initiative, and Batjes et al. (2024) provide a comprehensive breakdown of the monitoring component of MRV, along with an inventory and classification of current MRV methodologies, both without cost estimates. In the frame of MARVIC WP1, Lorand et al.

(2024) compared different existing methodological frameworks from seven different standards (Verra, Gold Standard, Plan Vivo, Label Bas Carbone, UK Woodland Carbon Code, UK Peatland Code, MoorFutures) in terms of quality, based on the following criteria: additionality, permanence, leakage risk, baseline, and the risk of double counting, but still without cost estimates. A report by the Umweltbundesamt (2021) to the EC reviewed the MRV and/or transaction costs of some international certification standards, and one conclusion is that they can easily overcome the anticipated revenues from CF schemes. De Cara et al. (2018) also estimated MRV costs based on different assumptions, including fixed and variable costs, for the purpose of their article. The central estimate could be used by first round of model runs in Task 5.1 models, and revised when the MRV costs are assessed more in detail in MARVIC using the protocols that are to be developed.

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7. Appendices

Appendix I Data collection methods

Three methods can be used to collect data on the costs and benefits associated with CF practices:

- **Expert-based method:** this approach is widely used to collect data on cost of production (CoP) of different crops and livestock (crop and livestock-specific costs and revenues) across many developed and developing countries (e.g. agri-benchmark network⁴). It involves consulting a panel of experts to first define one or more representative (typical or modal) farms that reflect different farming systems within the country or specific target regions. For each typical farm, the panel identifies all variable and fixed inputs required to implement a CF practice on a unit of land. Using this data, along with agricultural output and input unit prices from statistical databases, the CoP of CF practices can be calculated. The results of the cost computations can be presented to the panel for cross-checking, which may prompt revisions to the underlying parameters and initiate a new round of calculations. Panels typically include a selected group of farmers; representatives from cooperatives and farm associations; extension service workers; producers of agricultural inputs, machinery, and equipment; and researchers from agricultural institutions.
- **Survey-based method:** interviewing farmers is the preferred instrument for collecting data on farm activities (including crop-specific costs), although it is expensive and time consuming. It relies on statistical sampling and questionnaire inquiry and can be performed face-to-face, by telephone or online. **This method includes both stand-alone and multipurpose surveys.** Stand-alone surveys are tailored to meet a specific objective, such as gathering the cost of production (CoP) for crops or livestock. In contrast, multipurpose surveys (e.g., the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN)) are designed to gather comprehensive data on overall farm activities and various topics using a single data collection instrument. Both stand-alone and multipurpose surveys can be used to collect data on the costs and benefits of CF practices; however, careful attention should be given to the sampling strategy

⁴ <http://www.agribenchmark.org/agri%20benchmark/who-we-are.html>

to ensure that the sample is representative of key variables (such as CF practice type, farm size, and agro-ecological area). The primary advantage of this method, if the sample is well-designed, is that it allows for accurate estimation of the net effects of CF practices by comparing adopters and non-adopters with similar profiles.

- **Statistics-based method: this is a secondary data collection method that utilizes existing information from public statistics** (such as FADN and Eurostat data), **pre-existing research materials** (e.g., from the Pellerin & Bamière, et al. (2020) and Bamière et al. (2023) datasets⁵), **administrative records, and current CF initiatives** (e.g., Label Bas Carbone). This method is generally faster and more cost-effective than primary data collection (e.g., survey-based methods), though it may lack the same level of accuracy. For this reason, using multiple data sources is recommended whenever possible, allowing cross-checks between sources to improve consistency. This method is more suitable to estimate the implicit (hidden) costs (i.e. opportunity costs) of CF practices that are difficult to collect through the surveys.

⁵ <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/etude4pour1000>

Appendix II Cost and revenues for Cropland

Table 6. Average costs and revenues of carbon farming (CF) practices, compared to baseline (i.e., current practices): cropland

Cropland									
Cost category		Unit		Cover crops	Crop rotation	Low tillage	Zero tillage	Organic amendments	Residue management
Intermediate input costs	Seed and seeding purchased		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Inorganic fertiliser		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Organic fertiliser		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Herbicides		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Insecticides		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Fungicides		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Other Plant Protection Products		Quantity						
			Unit price						
Other specific costs		Quantity							
		Unit price							
Remuneration of external factors	Contract work		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Land rent paid		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Equipment rent paid		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Water (irrigation)		Quantity						
			Unit price						

			Unit price						
Overhead	Current upkeep of machinery and equipment		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Upkeep of land improvements and buildings		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Energy		Quantity						
			Unit price						
Insurance		Quantity							
		Unit price							
Other farming overhead		Quantity							
		Unit price							
Fixed costs	Depreciation for machinery and equipment		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Depreciation for agricultural land		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Depreciation for plantation		Quantity						
			Unit price						
Explicit indirect costs	Administrative costs		Quantity						
			Unit price						
	Explicit transaction costs		Quantity						
			Unit price						
Opportunity costs	Opportunity costs		Quantity						
			Unit price						
Implicit transaction costs	Transaction costs		Quantity						
			Unit price						
Other implicit costs	Yield reduction in next crop		Quantity						
			Unit price						

	Reduced inputs (labour, water, ...) for next crops	Quantity							
		Unit price							
Explicit revenues	Revenues from the sale of CF products	Quantity							
		Unit price							
	Revenues from selling carbon credit (e.g. rewarding payments)	Quantity							
		Unit price							
Government supports (e.g. subsidies, grants)	Quantity								
	Unit price								
Implicit revenues	Other generated revenues (i.e. input saving, extra-yield ...)	Quantity							
		Unit price							

Appendix III Agroforestry implementation cost

Table 7 Schedule of cash flows associated with the implementation of the Agroforestry practice, net present value (NPV) and constant annuity (CA). Discount rate 4.5%, table adapted from the Agroforestry spreadsheet in Bamière et al. (2022a, <https://doi.org/10.57745/10XJV0>)

Year	Plantation	Grass strip maintenance	Shaping pruning	Regar nishing	Thinning yr 10	Pruning yr 4 to 15	Sale of wood thinning	Sale of wood pruning yr 4 to 12	Sale of timber (stumpage)	Loss of cultivated area	Yield reduction	Total
NPV	1007	413	612	52	71	492	-161	-160	-3017	1 422,5	920	1651
CA	51	21	31	3	4	25	-8	-8	-153	72	46,5	84
0	1007	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1007
1	0	0	119	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	0	191
2	0	0	119	57	0	0	0	0	0	72	0	248
3	0	0	119	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	0	191
4	0	0	119	0	0	18	0	-9	0	72	0	200
5	0	0	119	0	0	36	0	-17	0	72	0	210
6	0	0	119	0	0	71	0	-34	0	72	0	228
7	0	29	0	0	0	71	0	-34	0	72	0	138
8	0	29	0	0	0	71	0	-34	0	72	0	138
9	0	29	0	0	0	71	0	-34	0	72	0	138
10	0	29	0	0	110	77	-250	-22	0	72	0	16
11	0	29	0	0	0	77	0	-22	0	72	0	156
12	0	29	0	0	0	77	0	-22	0	72	0	156
13	0	29	0	0	0	62	0	0	0	72	0	163
14	0	29	0	0	0	62	0	0	0	72	0	163
15	0	29	0	0	0	62	0	0	0	72	0	163
16	0	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	103	204
17	0	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	103	204
...
48	0	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	103	204
49	0	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	-26080	72	103	-25875

Appendix IV MRV cost breakdown in the example of the French Label Bas Carbone for Arable land

<p>1. Initial situation assessment of the farm</p>	<p>Training technicians from agricultural cooperatives to carry out analysis</p> <p>2 days' training for 10 to 15 technicians</p> <p>(1,5 days on site 0,5 days online)</p> <p>Training costs : 600€ per technician</p>
<p><i>Collection of historical and current activity data as well as soil data at the farm level and simulations using the Carbon Extract tool developed by Agrosolutions, certified field crop method of Label Bas Carbone. In this tool, SOC sequestration, for field crops, is estimated using SIMEOS-AMG, while GHG emissions are calculated according to the Label Bas Carbone methodology</i></p>	<p>On-farm diagnosis by the technician</p> <p>Labor approx. 500 € per day for a technician</p> <p>The technician spends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≈ 1 day for presentation to the farmer, travel to the farm, simulations for different combinations of practices + to enter the data into the tool + educational time with the farmer to identify which combination of practices he/she prefers to implement • ≈ 1 to 1.5 days for data collection, depending on data traceability on all the practices^[4] of the farm on all its plots over the last 3 years (if already listed in FMS^[2] or SMAG^[3] database or not) (and takes longer if GHGs removals are accounted for or not) <p>Where data is not available, use generic data from public databases. ^[4]This has no influence on the time spent by the technician, but it does have an influence on the uncertainty of the carbon sequestration. It should be noted that AMG simulations do not consider which data are generic or specific, and the inherent uncertainty is therefore not quantified. A discount is applied to the farmer's payment to take account of this uncertainty. This discount is 5 or 10%, depending on the number of generic or specific data.</p>

	<p>Purchase of the license of the tool (Carbon extract) by the cooperative</p> <p>2500 € by structure +270 € per technician</p> <p>(Cost to access AMG simulations in the tool, paid by Agrosolutions)</p>
	<p>Carbon sequestration monitoring</p> <p>½ day per year for a technician, to update activity and soil data and thus update the carbon sequestration trajectory</p>
<p>2.Project monitoring</p>	<p>No actual data available, but allow the technician a little time to give all the information to an auditor</p>
<p>3.Verification</p> <p><i>At the end of 5 years, estimate the quantity sequestered in order to sell the credit on the market</i></p>	

[1] Technical itinerary, sequestration practices already implemented, etc.

[2] FMS: farm management system, used by farmers for CAP subsidies. However, farmers are heterogeneous in terms of consistency and robustness of filling, this is why data is more or less traceable and takes more or less time to collect.

[3] SMAG is a subsidiary of Agrosolutions, developing agricultural technology tools (input optimization, etc.), so some farmers have already given their activity data for these tools.

[4] e.g. BDAT from Gis Sol for soil type, Enquêtes pratiques culturales at the departmental level for past yields, etc.

Cost paid by the farm for a diagnosis and monitoring with Carbon Extract

Diagnosis costs + simulation costs	Each farm pays 250€ to have results
Project monitoring	50 € per year per farm to keep the user interface active, to update activity data and thus update the sequestration trajectory
Total	At the farm scale, borne by the farmer: 250€ + 50€ per year = 500 € per farm for the 5 years of the project

Another tool : CAP2'ER

<p>Field crops method of CAP'2ER</p> <p><i>Initial situation assessment and monitoring according to the Label Bas Carbone field crops method: Collection of farm activity data and simulation of carbon sequestration with AMG</i></p> <p><i>This version of CAP'2ER was created a year ago. Previously, the tool was only intended to account for the livestock unit.</i></p>	<p>Training for data collection and simulations using the tool: 1090 € per technician paid by cooperatives and takes 2 days.</p> <p>Cost diagnosis at the farm: 50€ paid by structure (cooperative). Data collection and data entry into the tool are carried out by a technician and takes 1.5 or 2 days.</p>
<p>Livestock method of CAP'2ER</p> <p><i>Tool for calculating initial emissions related to livestock farming and designing an action plan on 5 years for the transition at the farm level, according to the Carbon Agri method</i></p>	<p>In addition to the training costs for technicians and the farm diagnostic cost, similar to the "Field Crops" method of CAP'2ER, this method includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A training cost for farmers at the beginning of the project, to teach them how to implement the practices. This cost is 60€ if the farmer is part of a training system, otherwise 250€. • There is a meeting halfway through the project, after 3 years, with the technician at the farm, to ensure mitigation practices are properly implemented • There is a final diagnostic at the farm, which, like the initial diagnostic, costs 50€ and is paid by the cooperative • In this method, the farmer does not pay anything, everything is subsidized by the cooperative

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